

A GLANCE AT THE CREATION OF THE GREAT PAINTER, RAFAELI OF THE EAST - KAMOLIDDIN BEHZOD

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Annotation: This article talks about the work of Kamoliddin Behzod, a great artist, a highly gifted scholar of the East, the founder of many new genres of art, one of the first manifestations of Eastern fine art. In the article, a lot of necessary information about the fact that the great heritage and scientific resources of the artist are still serving as the most necessary, main source of knowledge for us, and how the special school of art created by him is currently flourishing, is covered in scientific and artistic language .

Key words: painter, miniature, workshop, painter, graphic artist, art, national value, cultural heritage, calligraphy, cover artist, portrait

Uzbekistan is the heart of Central Asia and the development of science around the world it is the homeland of great scientists who made a great contribution. First of all, every nation is proud of its brave and selfless sons, great and thinkers, scientists and scholars who made a great contribution to human civilization. From this point of view, the pride of the Uzbek people is higher than the mountains. After all, the names of our great scholars who were born and raised in our country, who amazed the world with their extremely brilliant scientific and creative activities, fill our hearts with pride and pride. One can even write a book about the names of our great-grandfathers. One of them is the famous painter of Persian miniatures, our great ancestor Kamoliddin Behzod, who was the painter of the palaces of the Timurid ruler Husayn Boykara and later the Safavid king Takhmasp. He worked in the Timurid court during the Renaissance

and later entered the service of the Safavids in the royal workshops in Tabriz.

He was born in Herat around 1450 and died in Tabriz in 1535. Of the many works attributed to Behzod, only a few are by his hand recognized as created. He perfected the Persian miniature style and made it famous all over the world. Kamoliddin Behzod was the chief artist of the artist workshop in Herat. His position in the royal library was very high. Behzad's art is distinctive and incorporates generalized geometric attributes of Persian miniatures. He created his own style of painting. In his works, value and individuality of character are skillfully used.

The most reliable sources about the artist's life are the palace of Herat or the Safavids received from persons directly related to the palace. It is considered that reliable information has reached us from historical figures such as Khondamir, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, Dost Muhammad ibn Sulaiman, Mirza Haidar, Iskandar Munshi and Qazi Ahmed Qami. The information provided by the historians of the Ottoman state is distorted by various myths surrounding Kamaluddin Behzod and his works.

About the artist's life after the death of Husayn Boykara in 1506 information is scarce. In the work "Boburnoma" it is reported that Behzod entered the service of Muhammad Shaibani Khan in 1507-1510. There is also an anecdote about this, which is as follows: "Muhammad Shaibani Khan asked Kamoliddin Behzad to draw his portrait. Shaibani Khan, not satisfied with the result, finished the painting himself." It is not known how Kamaluddin Behzod entered the service of the Safavid dynasty, but when the young prince Tahmasp was the governor of Herat, he confirmed to be in service. The first document linking him to the Safavid palace is the decree on the appointment of Shah Ismail as the head of the royal workshop in 1522. This document has caused controversy among many scientists. There is a chronological inconsistency in the dating of the poetry collections in Khondamir's work "Name of the Name". Another document

connecting Behzad and Shah Ismail is an anecdote published in 1587 by the Ottoman scientist Mustafa Ali Galipoglu in his work "Manoqib ul-Hunarvaran". It depicts Behzad and the calligrapher Mahmud Nishapuri hiding in fear of the victory of the Ottomans in the Battle of Chaldiron. As it is combined with prophecies of an Ottoman victory, there are doubts about its historicity and authenticity

In addition, Safavid artists Dost Muhammad, Qazi Ahmed Qami and Iskandar Munshiyar said that Behzad's work was done by Shah Tahmasp without any connection with his predecessor.

they emphasize. According to Qazi Ahmad, Behzad came to Tabriz under the leadership of Sultan Ahmad when the Tahmasp library already existed. Therefore, some authors assume that the artist came to Tabriz only in 1524, when the new king ascended the throne. Authors A little information about Behzod's life in the Safavid court will give. The fact that he was placed at the head of the royal library, that is, all the artists, it is almost certain that he supervised the calligraphers, binders, etc. Shah worked in his workshop, and later developed the main directions of the style gave Qazi Ahmad said that Nizami's "Hamsa" was written by Shah Mahmud Nishapuri described with his calligraphy. It is Dost Muhammad who determines that Behzod died in the service of Tahmasp and was buried next to Sheikh Kamal in Tabriz in 669 AH (1535-1536).

He ends his life in the Safavid palace, surrounded by family members. His his nephew is the calligrapher Rustam Ali, who followed the artist's teachings in Tabriz his nephews Muhib Ali and Muzaffar Ali are also artists in the Safavid court those who worked. Among his students were Shaikhzada, Kasim Ali, Agha Mirak and there were others. Only one manuscript contains pictures with his personal signature, considered by all modern scholars to be a real giant: the work "The Garden" was specially prepared by Sa'diy Shirozi for the Hossein Boykara library. This five illustrations in the book were made by Behzod. The colophon is

signed by the scribe Sultan Ali Mashhadi, and two of the miniatures are dated 1488-1489. Methodically to Kamoliddin Behzod or his close friends in Herat some other related works are:

A copy of "Boston" by Saadi Shirazy in 1478; Written by Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi in 1467 and to Husayn Boygaro copy of "Zafarnoma" dedicated to By the Mongol emperor Jahangir classified in India, with many changes, and said to contain eight miniatures painted by Behzad; Farididdin Attar's picture in "Mantiq ut-tayr" in 1483; Alisher Navoi's "Khamsa" of 1485, the son of Husayn Boykara Image dedicated to Badiuzzamon; A picture of Amir Khusrav Dehlavi for the work "Khamsa" in 1485; Illustration made in 1486 for Shirozi's work "Gulistan"; Two pictures for Nizami Ganjavi's work "Khamsa"; Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on November 6, 2020 State scholarship named after Kamoliddin Behzod was established to encourage talented students in the fields of easel painting, painting, graphics and miniatures, sculpture, applied art, design, art history and museology. Kamoliddin Behzod's famous works - "Amir Temur and Egypt The Battle of the Mamluk Sultan, "Yusuf and Zulayha", a miniature painting from "Iskandarnama", "Sultan Husayn", "Amir Temur's accession to the throne", "Dancing Dervishes" are included. Kamoliddin Behzad contributed to the development of the visual arts his unique painted works still amaze the world. The works created by the great artist have always served as a source of inspiration and an example for many artists. Artists such as Sultan Muhammad, Qasim Ali, Maulana Darvesh Muhammad scientists made a significant contribution to the development of the Eastern miniature school. The work of Kamoliddin Behzod will have an important place not only in the development of our national art, but also in the further spiritual development of our people.

REFERENCES

1. National encyclopedia of Uzbekistan. The first volume. Tashkent, 2000.

2. Book-album "Kamoluddin Behzod, who embarrassed Moni".
3. Usmanov O., Madraimov A., Kamoliddin Behzod, T., 2000; Koziyev T., Behzod and civilization. T., 2000
4. Norkulov N., Nizomutdinova I., Scenes from the history of miniatures, T., 1970